

Appendix: Commensurating Abend's incommensurables

We here translate Abend's types using our conception as a Rosetta stone. For clarity, we mark our 'translations' *theory 1_x*, *theory 2_x*, *theory 3_x*, and so on. The point of the exercise is not to produce a more attractive typology than Abend's, but simply to show that his theory types have important common features and that those features are captured by our conception of theory.

The translations are presented in full below and shown in brief in Table 1, together with notes that schematically indicate the translation procedure. Underlined words in the "Translation procedure" column are the elements we added to our minimal definition to maintain the core of Abend's types in translation. They tell us what our minimal theory of theory does not capture in each type, and therefore what is special about it as a type of theory. We have also added in parenthesis some types of action that are done with or to the different theory types that were integrated in Abend's typology but disentangled in translation.

Theory 1 refers to "a general proposition, or logically-connected system of general propositions, which establishes a relationship between two or more variables" (Abend, 2008, p. 177). Abend adds that such a theory deals with its variables "*in general*, independently of things like time and space" (ibid); examples include Durkheim's ([1897] 1951) theory of suicide and Parsons and Shills' (1951) theory of social action. Our translated *theory 1_x* refers to a set of general assumptions about the relationship between abstract phenomena. We treated 'propositions' simply as 'assumptions'. We treated 'variables' as 'abstract phenomena' (as variables refer to properties such as gender or education, and properties are, widely conceived, phenomena). The underlined words 'general' and 'abstract' indicate that these theories' assumptions are not specific and that their phenomena are not concrete.

Theory 2 refers to "an explanation of a particular social phenomenon" (Abend 2008:178). For example, a theory 2 "of the stock market crash of October 1929 tells one what brought it about" (ibid). Our translated *theory 2_x* refers to a set of assumptions about a particular phenomenon. Like 'theory', 'explanation' has multiple meanings in sociology, but Abend provides no further clarification (and in this, he is in good company). We can infer from his examples that theories 2 contain assumptions about *causal* relationships between phenomena, but to explain can also mean to clarify what something is like (cf. Abbott, 2004, pp. 8–12). We therefore treat 'an explanation' as 'an account of the assumptions ascribed to particular phenomena and/or its relationship to other phenomena'. It is, after all, the sum of the

accounted assumptions that does whatever it is we expect explanations to do. The word ‘explanation’ is therefore not included in the translation, but the general function it refers to is. We added ‘particular’ to indicate that theories of this kind deal with particular phenomena (e.g., ‘the stock market crash of October 1929’) as opposed to general phenomena (e.g., ‘market crashes’ or ‘economic change’).

Theory 3 refers to theories that “offer (...) an original ‘interpretation,’ ‘reading,’ or ‘way of making sense’ of a certain slice of the empirical world” (Abend 2008:178). The translated *theory 3_x* refers to an *original set of assumptions about phenomena in a particular part of the world*.¹ As with ‘explanation’ above, ‘interpretation’ can mean a number of things and Abend provides no further specification. We therefore treat ‘interpretation’ as an ‘account of assumptions about phenomena’. Note that ‘interpretation’ is thus translated exactly like ‘explanation’ – not because it is unimportant and not because the words necessarily mean the same – in fact, they are markers of stylistic camps in sociology – but because, for the task of capturing Abend’s theory type, we can maintain the function using the core elements of our general conception. The phrase ‘a certain slice of the empirical world’ is treated as ‘phenomena in a particular slice of the world’. Finally, as our translation no longer includes the word ‘interpretation’, ‘original’ is treated as related to the set of assumptions of the theory in question. For precision, it could be added that original assumptions often highlight *novel* phenomena – as in Goffman’s (1974) theory of framing – or, at least, *shed new light on* established phenomena – as in Goffman’s (1963) theory of stigma.

Theory 4 refers to “the study of and the students of the writings of authors such as Marx, Weber, Durkheim, Simmel, Parsons, Habermas, or Bourdieu” (Abend 2008:179). Abend adds that “you cannot *have, have developed, or put forward* a [theory 4]” (ibid), because it refers as much to the people studying classic works as it does to any result of those studies. Here we disagree with Abend’s semantic analysis. As mentioned in the article, we agree that sociologists refer to students and teachers of the (neo)classics as ‘theorists’, their field as ‘theory’ and their work as ‘theoretical’ or ‘theory work’. But what sociologists mean by that, we think, is that their engagement with studies by famous theoreticians is what makes their

¹ It is difficult to know from Abend’s typology whether “a certain slice of the empirical world” refers to something more or less general than the “particular social phenomenon” of theory 2. If we assume that “the finance sector” could be considered “a slice of the empirical world”, then theory 3 deals with phenomena that are more general than theory 2 – but perhaps not as abstract as theory 1. At any rate, the distinction is perhaps more in the implied difference between theories that interpret and theories that explain. We are, however, not convinced that this difference is 1) clear and 2) incommensurable. We think instead that types 2 and 3 allude to different styles of empirically oriented sociological work.

field ‘theory’, their work ‘theoretical’, and themselves ‘theorists’. Consequently, we propose the following (not very musical) translation: (*studies, alterations or articulations of*) existing sets of assumptions about phenomena found in (neo)classical works. The bracketed phrase ‘studies, alterations or articulations of’ is intended to disentangle the (neo)classical theories from what is done to them. The theoretical assumptions already exist (hence the underlining), and the activity involves either studying them or formalizing and altering them. We believe this more accurately captures what sociologists mean when referring to the study of, say, Weber, as ‘doing theory’.

Theory 5 refers to “an overall perspective from which one sees and interprets the world” (Abend 2008:179) and is exemplified with approaches such as feminist theory, queer theory, game theory and poststructuralist theory, to name but a few.² Our translated *theory 5_X* refers to *a set of assumptions about phenomena* (that are used as a perspective).³ As elaborated in the article, the bracketed phrase ‘that are used as a perspective’ disentangles the theory in theory 5 from how it is used. In principle, any set of assumptions may (be deliberately used to) affect how you “see” some phenomena, or how you perceive and reason about it. To the extent that far from all theories regularly play such a role in research, however, theory 5_X should perhaps be specified as referring to only those *theories that are typically used as a perspective*.

Theory 6 refers to “accounts that have a fundamental normative component” (Abend 2008:180). The main feature, then, is that these types of theories are not merely descriptive but include evaluative components (e.g., Marx’ theory of capitalism and exchange). The translated *theory 6_X* refers to *a set of assumptions about a phenomenon, where normative*

² Abend emphasizes that, in contrast to theory 1, 2 and 3, theories 5 “are not about the social world itself, but about how to look at, grasp, and represent it” (2008:179), yet his chosen examples does not fit well with his description. That is, we are not convinced that sociologists actually use ‘theory’ to convey versions of, say, game theory or poststructuralism, that are not about the social world. Although abstract, the ‘games’ of game theory (e.g., *chicken*) and the liquid ‘structures’ of poststructuralist theory (e.g., *discourses*) are certainly not limited to matters *outside* the social realm. We find that Abend’s examples point to phenomena in the social realm about which one can have assumptions (e.g., social situations or discourses), and therefore that they conform well enough with our general conception of theory. We therefore focus our translatory efforts on the ‘perspective’ aspect of theory 5. (On a different note, Abend (2008:180) also exemplifies theory 5 with categories of thought that are “logically prior to any contact with the social world”, which forces the question of whether the examples are sufficiently similar to justify the type).

³ Note that theory 5_X (*a set of assumptions about phenomena* (that are used as a perspective’) now becomes almost indistinguishable from theory 1_X (*a set of general assumptions about the relationship between abstract phenomena*), in sharp contrast to Abend’s original types. Any experienced sociologist using Abend’s original typology could easily get a clear sense of different types of sociological work when thinking about, e.g., theory 1 (e.g., Durkheim’s theory of suicide) and theory 5 (e.g., ‘postmodern theories’). But the main difference, from our perspective, is not in incommensurable types of theory, but precisely in substantively different styles of sociological work.

assumptions are a central component. Abend's "fundamental normative component" is thus treated as relating to the normative character of a theory's assumptions (e.g., 'equality is good' or 'domination and exchange is wrong').

Finally, *theory 7* refers to "the study of certain special problems that sociology has encountered", exemplified with, among others, the "micro-macro problem", and the "problem of structure and agency" (ibid). Based on his description and choice of examples, Abend's "certain special problems" are what are also called foundational problems, and the translated *theory 7_x* therefore refers to (articulations or alterations of) *assumptions about abstract phenomena that are involved in a foundational problem of sociology*. From our view, what seems to set this theory type apart for Abend is their subject matter and the position of the ongoing debates they feature in. But as theories, they nevertheless seem to conform well with our minimal conception of theory.

References

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